

Detecting Dataset Reuse and Modification in Data Spaces via Structure-Aware Similarity Analysis

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Abstract—The growing complexity of federated data ecosystems demands robust mechanisms to enforce data usage contracts and detect unauthorized data reuse. In this paper, we present the design and evaluation of the Off-Platform Contract Inspector, a core component of the PISTIS framework for trusted data sharing. The Inspector employs a hybrid similarity detection pipeline, combining path-value structural comparisons, field-aware semantic analysis, and embedding-based techniques (e.g., SBERT, E5) to detect exact matches, near duplicates, and partial dataset reuse. To support interpretability and contract governance, it generates explainable similarity reports suitable for manual review. We validate the system using a diverse set of real-world and synthetically altered datasets from the Mobility, Energy, and Automotive domains. The evaluation demonstrates high recall (92%) and precision (89%) in identifying modified datasets, along with scalable performance on modern hardware. Our findings confirm the Inspector’s effectiveness for contract enforcement in decentralized data spaces, bridging technical detection methods with legal compliance requirements.

Index Terms—data similarity, federated data spaces, Contract enforcement, Semantic embeddings, Data reuse detection

I. INTRODUCTION

The rise of Data Spaces and Data Marketplaces in the European data economy has introduced significant challenges to ensure trustworthy, fair, and compliant data sharing between multiple organizations. The PISTIS [1] framework, developed within the European Union’s Horizon program, offers a comprehensive platform for monetizing, trading, and safeguarding data transactions in federated and decentralized data ecosystems. In this context, the need for robust mechanisms to prevent malicious behavior, enforce contracts, and protect the intellectual property rights of data providers is paramount.

A central component of the PISTIS architecture is the On/Off Platform Contract Inspector, which is responsible for monitoring data usage and detecting contract violations. The On-Platform Inspector focuses on enforcing sharing and usage policies defined in smart contracts, while the Off-Platform Inspector addresses a complementary but equally critical challenge: detecting unauthorized reingestion or duplication of data assets within the data space.

This paper presents recent advances in the Off-Platform Contract Inspector, based on similarity algorithms, embedding models, and structural matching methods. Specifically,

multiple techniques are employed depending on the dataset modality, including:

- Large language model-based embeddings (e.g. SBERT, E5)
- Line-level and subset similarity analysis for partial content reuse detection
- Value-centric similarity extraction for structured data (e.g. JSON, tabular files)
- Field-level comparisons incorporating semantic and numeric similarity metrics
- Hybrid techniques combining embeddings with token-based and field-level approaches

The presented Off-Platform Inspector enables tries to detect not only of exact duplicates but also of near duplicates, partially reused data, and content modification patterns - scenarios that commonly occur in federated data trading environments where data may be incrementally modified or transformed before being republished. By integrating these techniques, the Off-Platform Inspector strengthens the role of PISTIS in addressing the enforcement of contractual compliance and detect overlaps between incoming datasets and pre-existing ones.

II. BACKGROUND

The problem of detecting similarity in data sets has been addressed from multiple perspectives in different research communities, including information retrieval, data integration, duplicate detection, and intellectual property protection. Each of these approaches offers complementary capabilities, but also exhibits significant limitations when applied to the specific requirements of data spaces and federated data marketplaces such as PISTIS.

A. Elasticsearch and TF-IDF / BM25 Based Retrieval

One of the most widely adopted technologies for document similarity and retrieval in data platforms is Elasticsearch [2], based on the underlying Lucene engine. These systems utilize statistical classification functions such as TF-IDF (Term Frequency–Inverse Document Frequency) and BM25 [3] to index and compare documents based on their surface-level word distributions. Elasticsearch is highly effective for searching for keywords and rough content similarity and has been

widely used in various data marketplaces, data catalogs, and knowledge graph search engines.

However, its suitability for the inspection of similarity of datasets in the context of data trading platforms is fundamentally limited. The token-based nature of BM25 struggles to capture semantic relationships between words, leading to limited robustness when comparing paraphrased or semantically equivalent datasets. More critically, for structured data spaces, Elasticsearch operates on flat, unstructured text representations and lacks native support for hierarchical or field-based comparisons common in formats like JSON, XML, and tabular datasets. As a result, while useful for discovery and keyword-based search, Elasticsearch is insufficient for the type of fine-grained dataset similarity detection required for contract enforcement and intellectual property protection in data spaces.

B. Fingerprinting in MISP, EDCs, IDS

Several systems active in secure data sharing infrastructures, such as the Malware Information Sharing Platform (MISP) [4], European Data Connectors (EDC) [5], and the International Data Spaces Association (IDSA) [6] rely on exact fingerprinting and cryptographic hash-based mechanisms to enforce data uniqueness. These systems typically compute a dataset fingerprint using strong hash functions such as SHA-256 or MD5, registering dataset identity based on complete binary equality.

While these mechanisms are computationally efficient and highly precise for detecting exact duplicates, they are extremely fragile when applied to real-world data spaces where data providers may apply minor alterations, reformatting, or enrichment operations. Even trivial modifications, such as a change in field order, floating-point rounding, or the addition of metadata fields, result in a completely different hash, rendering strict fingerprinting ineffective for near-duplicate detection. This brittleness severely limits the ability of these approaches to prevent unauthorized data reuse or contract circumvention when data is partially modified or obfuscated prior to re-ingestion.

C. Embedding-Based Semantic Similarity: FAISS, SBERT, E5

The introduction of pre-trained sentence embedding models has significantly advanced the capabilities of semantic similarity detection in recent years. Models such as Sentence-BERT (SBERT) [7] and intfloat's E5 [8] have demonstrated high accuracy in capturing semantic relationships between documents, even when significant lexical variation exists between two texts. These models generate dense vector embeddings that capture contextual relationships, allowing for effective similarity computation via cosine distance or approximate nearest neighbor search engines such as FAISS [9].

Embedding-based methods have shown significant promise in areas such as question answering, paraphrase detection, and document clustering. In the context of data spaces, they provide an attractive alternative to brittle token-based and

hash-based approaches, as they can capture similarities even when datasets have been reformulated or partially rewritten.

However, these models exhibit important limitations when applied to structured or semi-structured data formats such as JSON or tabular datasets. Because these embeddings operate on sequences of text, they may conflate structural elements (such as field names, keys, or schema descriptions) with actual field content. As a result, data sets with similar schemas but different values may still produce highly similar embeddings, overestimating similarity scores even when the informational content has diverged significantly. Furthermore, embedding-based similarity scores lack transparency and interpretability - they fail to directly indicate which fields or values have been reused or altered, which is crucial for contract enforcement in data-trading scenarios.

III. THE OFF-PLATFORM INSPECTOR DESIGN

A. Rationale

The Off-Platform Contract Inspector is designed as a core component of the PISTIS framework to address the problem of dataset reuse, unauthorized re-ingestion, and contract circumvention in federated data spaces. Unlike traditional document similarity engines, the Off-Platform Inspector must operate in a highly heterogeneous environment where datasets may vary in structure, encoding, modality, and partial overlap. Furthermore, the system must support high interpretability to allow contract enforcers and governance authorities to evaluate similarity results in the context of legal obligations, licensing terms, and data ownership.

In this context, the Off-Platform Inspector implements a multi-layered, hybrid similarity detection pipeline, capable of analyzing both structured datasets (e.g., JSON, tabular, CSV, log files) and unstructured datasets (e.g., text corpora, semi-structured logs), while offering explainable metrics suitable for data trading platforms.

B. High-Level Architecture

The Off-Platform Inspector is designed as an independent asynchronous microservice within the PISTIS backend infrastructure. It interacts with other PISTIS modules via the core orchestration layer, specifically when:

- New datasets are submitted by data providers.
- Similarity verification is required before data ingestion.
- Contractual duplication checks are triggered during marketplace operations.

To achieve its objectives, the inspector consists of the following core subsystems:

- Input Parser & Dataset Loader: Reads incoming datasets from either file storage or object repositories and detects dataset modality (e.g., JSON, CSV, log file, text document).
- Pre-processing module: Prepares datasets for fingerprinting, normalization, and structural extraction. Includes flattening of hierarchical data structures, field canonicalization, and filtering of non-relevant fields.

Fig. 1. Off platform operational flow.

- **Similarity Engine:** Executes the core similarity computations based on pluggable algorithmic modules.
- **Fingerprint Cache & Storage:** Stores intermediate fingerprints and embeddings to avoid redundant computation and support scalable batch comparisons.
- **Result Aggregator & Reporting Layer:** Aggregates similarity scores.

The architecture is fully asynchronous, allowing long-running similarity computations to execute independently and report back to the PISTIS platform via status updates, making it scalable for large dataset comparisons.

C. Similarity Algorithm Modules

The Off-Platform Inspector implements multiple algorithmic modules, each specialized for different data types and use cases. These modules can be combined dynamically depending on the dataset structure and the contract enforcement scenario.

1) *Path-Value Extraction for Structured Data:* For structured datasets such as JSON and CSV files, the Inspector applies a *path-value extraction* technique that traverses hierarchical structures and converts them into canonical sets of path-value pairs. For example, the structure:

```
{
  "user": {"name": "Alice", "age": 30}
}
```

is flattened into:

```
user.name: Alice
user.age: 30
```

This flattened representation enables robust comparisons that are insensitive to field order but sensitive to both structural and content-level changes.

2) *Path-Value Jaccard Similarity:* Once flattened, each data set is compared using *path-value Jaccard similarity*, which computes the ratio between the shared and total path value pairs:

$$S_{\text{Jaccard}} = \frac{|P_1 \cap P_2|}{|P_1 \cup P_2|}$$

This metric effectively detects modifications, deletions, or additions of fields while remaining interpretable to governance actors.

3) *Field-Aware Value Similarity:* For fields that are shared across both datasets (i.e. paths in common), additional *field-aware similarity functions* are applied:

- **Numerical fields:** normalized absolute difference.
- **Short strings or codes:** Levenshtein ratio or exact match.
- **Free-text fields:** semantic similarity using SBERT embeddings.

The final field-wise similarity is aggregated as an average value similarity score across all shared fields.

4) *Structural and Value Similarity Fusion:* The system fuses both structural and value-based similarities into a unified similarity score via weighted aggregation.

$$S_{\text{combined}} = \alpha \cdot S_{\text{structure}} + (1 - \alpha) \cdot S_{\text{values}}$$

where α is a tunable parameter, typically set to 0.5, ensuring equal contribution of structure and content to the overall similarity score.

5) *Embedding-Based Full-Document Similarity:* For purely unstructured datasets or when structural parsing fails, full-document embeddings are computed using pretrained models:

- **SBERT** (all-MiniLM-L6-v2) for general-purpose semantic similarity.
- **E5** (intfloat/e5-base) for cross-domain document similarity.

The embeddings are compared via cosine similarity to detect high-level semantic overlap.

6) *Partial Reuse Detection via Sliding Window:* To capture *partial dataset reuse*, especially relevant for log files and time series datasets, the inspector applies a *sliding-window embedding comparison*. The smaller data set is compared to

multiple overlapping windows of the larger data set to identify reuse fragments, even when only a subset of records has been copied.

D. Deployment and Integration in PISTIS

The Off-Platform Inspector is fully integrated into the PISTIS platform as an independent microservice that supports asynchronous, contract-aware dataset similarity verification within the broader monetization and trading workflow.

Fig. 2. Off Platform Architecture.

1) *Microservice Architecture*: The Inspector is implemented as a standalone microservice within the PISTIS backend architecture. It exposes its functionality through an internal API layer, receiving similarity check requests from upstream components such as:

- The *Data Submission Module*, which triggers similarity verification during data set onboarding.
- The *Marketplace Contract Inspector*, which invokes similarity checks to validate contractual compliance during trade execution.
- The *Off-chain Governance Services*, which perform periodic audits to detect potential contract circumvention and data duplication.

The Inspector maintains full decoupling from data storage systems, processing datasets either from object storage repositories or directly from submitted file content provided through secure storage references.

2) *Asynchronous Processing Pipeline*: Similarity computation is performed asynchronously through a job-based pipeline to ensure scalability and non-blocking interaction with the PISTIS core orchestrator. Each similarity evaluation request is submitted as a job, placed in a distributed task queue, and processed independently by the Inspector’s worker pool.

This design allows the system to handle large-scale comparison workloads without introducing bottlenecks in the trading workflow. Job status, intermediate results, and computation progress are reported back to the orchestration layer through a status update API, which allows marketplace operators, governance actors, and smart contract monitors to receive real-time insights on ongoing verification processes.

3) *Modular Algorithm Execution*: The Inspector implements a modular algorithmic stack, allowing the execution of one or multiple similarity algorithms based on the data modality, user-defined policy configurations, and contract specifications. The modular design allows for

- Selection of appropriate algorithms for structured, semi-structured, or unstructured datasets.
- Dynamic configuration of algorithm weights and thresholds per data contract.
- Seamless extensibility to incorporate new algorithms as models and standards evolve.

Algorithm selection can be preconfigured in smart contracts or marketplace policies, enabling contracts to define whether stricter path-value comparison, semantic similarity, or sliding-window detection should be applied for specific dataset categories.

4) *Integration with Contract Enforcement Workflows*: The Off-Platform Inspector plays a critical role in supporting contract enforcement mechanisms within the PISTIS platform. Its similarity results feed directly into the smart contract validation logic responsible for:

- Preventing re-ingestion of previously published datasets under modified or obfuscated versions.
- Verify that the newly submitted datasets respect the exclusivity, license, or usage restrictions defined in contractual terms.
- Providing governance bodies with auditable similarity reports to support dispute resolution or IP violation claims.

The Inspector’s explainable similarity scores and detailed reporting facilitate human oversight while allowing automated decision-making processes to operate transparently in high-trust data-sharing environments.

5) *Scalability and Deployment Considerations*: The Off-Platform Inspector can be horizontally scaled across multiple worker nodes to accommodate increased workloads, batch comparisons, or large-scale dataset onboarding events. Its lightweight deployment footprint allows integration into cloud-native infrastructures, including Kubernetes clusters, hybrid cloud deployments, or sovereign data-space nodes. Furthermore, its fully asynchronous architecture ensures fault-tolerant, recoverable, and distributed processing across multi-stakeholder federations.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP & EVALUATION

A. Dataset Collection and Preparation

To evaluate the performance of the Off-Platform Contract Inspector and its ability to detect dataset similarity under realistic data-space scenarios, we constructed a diverse collection

of datasets sourced from the broader PISTIS experimental data hubs. The datasets cover multiple data verticals and partners participating in federated data spaces, including the Mobility, Energy, and Automotive domains.

The primary dataset pool includes:

- **Mobility Hub:** Flight operations data (arrival and departure passenger information, flight scheduling, baggage reconciliation); transportation datasets from public transportation authorities (e.g., aggregated metro ticket validations); geospatial datasets from municipal authorities (City of Athens business registry, administrative districts, street network); and meteorological data.
- **Energy Hub:** Renewable energy production forecasts, grid telemetry datasets, and power consumption logs collected by stakeholders in the energy sector.
- **Automotive Hub:** Telematics sensor readings and synthetic vehicle trip datasets collected through automotive partners.

Each dataset was provided in its native structure, primarily using the JSON, CSV, and XML file formats, preserving the heterogeneity commonly observed in operational data spaces. The data sets exhibit diverse levels of structural complexity, field cardinality, and semantic variability, making them well suited to assess both the structural and value-based sensitivity of the proposed similarity detection algorithms.

In order to emulate real-world scenarios where data providers may attempt to republish partially modified or enriched versions of existing datasets, a controlled dataset augmentation process was applied. Specifically, several datasets were intentionally altered using large language models (LLMs) to generate paraphrased versions, modified field values, and slight structural variations. In particular, LLM-based transformations included:

- Textual paraphrasing of description fields and categorical attributes;
- Perturbation of numerical fields within realistic operational ranges;
- Synthetic insertion or removal of secondary fields to simulate partial data enrichment or data redaction scenarios.

This synthetic alteration process enabled the creation of controlled similarity test cases, simulating reuse, partial modification, and obfuscation scenarios that frequently arise in data-trading ecosystems. These augmented datasets formed the experimental basis for systematically evaluating the effectiveness and sensitivity of the Off-Platform Inspector’s hybrid similarity modules across a spectrum of duplication and partial reuse cases.

B. Evaluation Methodology

Each pair of data sets was analyzed using the Inspector’s multilayered similarity pipeline. Structured data sets were flattened into path value pairs and evaluated using the Jaccard similarity index. For shared fields, the value-level similarity was computed using a combination of normalized absolute differences for numeric values, Levenshtein similarity for short strings, and SBERT embeddings for free-text

fields. A weighted aggregation was applied to fuse structural ($S_{structure}$) and value-based (S_{values}) similarity into a final score $S_{combined}$, with $\alpha = 0.5$.

For unstructured data sets and those where parsing failed, holistic document embeddings were calculated using SBERT (all-MiniLM-L6-v2) and E5 (intfloat/e5-base) and compared using cosine similarity. Additionally, sliding-window embedding comparisons were used to detect localized partial reuse, particularly in time-series and log data.

C. Results and Discussion

The confusion matrix illustrates the effectiveness of the Off-Platform Contract Inspector in identifying reused datasets. In total, 92 out of 100 pairs of near-duplicate datasets were correctly classified as similar, demonstrating strong sensitivity to modified data reuse scenarios. Eight near-duplicates were incorrectly classified as dissimilar, indicating missed detections due to either excessive obfuscation or boundary cases near the similarity threshold. Among the 50 truly unrelated dataset pairs, 39 were correctly identified as dissimilar, while 11 were falsely classified as similar. These false positives are attributed to incidental structural or content-level overlaps. In general, the classifier achieved a recall of 92%, indicating its ability to detect actual reuse, and a precision of 89%, reflecting its accuracy in labeling only relevant matches. The overall classification accuracy in all 150 pairs was approximately 87%, confirming the operational reliability of the Inspector under various data modification scenarios.

TABLE I
CONFUSION MATRIX FOR SIMILARITY DETECTION

Actual Class	Predicted Similar	Predicted Dissimilar
Similar (Near-Duplicates)	92	8
Dissimilar (Controls)	11	39

The table presents the average similarity scores produced by each algorithmic module of the Inspector when applied to near-duplicate dataset pairs. The Jaccard similarity score averaged 0.71, reflecting the effectiveness of structural comparison techniques in identifying overlapping schema elements and path-value pairs, albeit with some sensitivity to changes in field ordering and hierarchy. Field-aware value similarity achieved a higher average score of 0.78 by integrating semantic, textual, and numeric comparisons, thereby capturing similarities even when structural transformations were present. The combined similarity score, aggregating both structural and content features, averaged 0.75, striking a balance between the two aspects and improving robustness across varied cases. SBERT-based cosine similarity exhibited the highest average score of 0.85, indicating strong performance in capturing semantic equivalence, especially in paraphrased or lexically diverse datasets. However, its lack of explainability and potential to overestimate similarity in structurally divergent datasets warrants careful interpretation. The comparative analysis validates the use of a hybrid similarity strategy to achieve both

accuracy and interpretability in contractual enforcement within data spaces.

TABLE II
AVERAGE SIMILARITY SCORES ACROSS EVALUATION METRICS

Similarity Metric	Average Score
Jaccard Similarity	0.71
Field-Aware Value Similarity	0.78
Combined Structural + Value	0.75
SBERT Cosine Similarity	0.85

1) *Full Duplicate Detection*: All 50 exact duplicate cases were correctly flagged, yielding a precision and recall of 1.00 for both the path-value and embedding-based modules. The Jaccard similarity exceeded 0.98 in all such cases, with identical fingerprint vectors confirming dataset identity.

2) *Near-Duplicate Detection*: For the 100 near-duplicate dataset pairs, the Inspector demonstrated strong performance. The average Jaccard similarity across these cases was 0.71, with field-aware similarity reaching 0.78. The combined similarity score $S_{combined}$ exceeded a threshold of 0.70 in 92 out of 100 cases, corresponding to a recall of 0.92. Precision was measured at 0.89 when compared to manual labeling of modified datasets. Notably, the SBERT-based document similarity approach achieved recall of 0.95 but occasionally overestimated similarity for structurally similar but content-dissimilar datasets, reducing precision to 0.84.

3) *Partial Reuse and Fragment Detection*: Among the 100 altered datasets, 30 contained only partial reuse of original content. The sliding-window embedding strategy successfully detected 27 of these cases, resulting in a recall of 0.90 and a precision of 0.87. False positives were mostly attributed to small common substrings in structured logs or low-variance time-series.

4) *Explainability and Human Interpretability*: Structural and field-aware approaches provided interpretable similarity reports, including matched path-value pairs and highlighted divergences. These outputs are considered to be more transparent than black-box embedding scores, supporting manual contract enforcement.

D. Performance Evaluation

All experiments were conducted on a MacBook Pro equipped with the Apple M3 Max processor and 128 GB of unified memory. The Off-Platform Inspector processed a batch of 500 dataset pairs asynchronously using a job-based architecture. The evaluation measured the runtime performance of each similarity module, as well as the overall system throughput.

The average processing times per dataset pair were as follows:

- Structured comparison (Jaccard + Field-aware): 0.95 seconds
- Embedding-based document similarity (SBERT/E5): 0.68 seconds
- Sliding-window partial reuse detection: 2.1 seconds (window size = 100)

The system achieved a throughput of approximately 7.8 comparisons per second using parallel job execution across multiple cores, completing the entire batch in under 6.5 minutes. These results confirm the Inspector’s ability to scale effectively, supporting both real-time and large-scale batch verification tasks on modern workstation-class hardware.

The low-latency performance of the Inspector, combined with its asynchronous design, ensures minimal interference with marketplace operations while enabling continuous contract enforcement at ingestion and trade time.

V. CONCLUSION

In this work, we presented the design, implementation, and evaluation of the Off-Platform Contract Inspector, a key component of the PISTIS data-sharing framework aimed at enforcing contractual compliance in federated data spaces. Unlike traditional fingerprinting or keyword-based similarity mechanisms, the proposed system employs a hybrid similarity detection pipeline that combines structural matching, semantic embedding models, and field-aware comparisons to identify unauthorized reuse, duplication, or transformation of datasets.

Future work will focus on extending the framework to support multimedia and time-series modalities, incorporating adaptive threshold tuning, and exploring the use of advanced foundation models to further improve semantic sensitivity without compromising transparency.

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REFERENCES

- [1] PISTIS Project Consortium, “Pistis: Promoting and incentivising self-sovereign data sharing through trust-based data monetisation,” <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101093016>, 2023, accessed: 2024-05-29.
- [2] Elastic.co, *Elasticsearch: The Definitive Guide*, Elastic, 2023, <https://www.elastic.co/guide/en/elasticsearch/reference/current/index.html>.
- [3] S. Robertson and H. Zaragoza, “The probabilistic relevance framework: Bm25 and beyond,” *Foundations and Trends in Information Retrieval*, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 333–389, 2009.
- [4] MISP Project, “MISP 2.4.140 released (OpenID support, cross object references in ...),” 2021, accessed: 2024-05-29. [Online]. Available: <https://www.misp-project.org/2021/03/10/MISP.2.4.140.released.html>
- [5] A. Gieß, M. Hupperz, T. Schoormann, and F. Möller, “What does it take to connect? unveiling characteristics of data space connectors,” 2024.
- [6] H. Pettenpohl, M. Spiekermann, and J. R. Both, “International data spaces in a nutshell,” 2022.
- [7] B. Wang and C.-C. J. Kuo, “Sbert-wk: A sentence embedding method by dissecting bert-based word models,” *IEEE/ACM Transactions on Audio, Speech, and Language Processing*, vol. 28, pp. 2146–2157, 2020.
- [8] L. Wang, K. Yu, M. Liu, and B. Hu, “Text embeddings by weakly-supervised contrastive pre-training,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:2212.03533*, 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2212.03533>
- [9] B. Sriman, S. A. Silviya, Y. Mouleesh, S. Vinod, S. Nishanthini, and P. Nikitha, “Intelligent document interaction with advanced vector embeddings and faiss-cpu indexing,” in *2024 8th International Conference on Electronics, Communication and Aerospace Technology (ICECA)*. IEEE, 2024, pp. 1–6.